

Chemical Investigation of the High Boiling Bases from Anthracene Oil.

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No systematic investigation regarding the isolation and identification of the high boiling bases occurring in anthracene oil appears to have been made so far, though 3:5- and 2:4-dimethylpyridines, 1-amino-2:4-dimethylpyridine, 2:3:6-trimethylpyridine, 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine (Eckert and Loria, *Monatsh.*, 1917, **38**, 225), 2:3:4:5-tetramethylpyridine, 2:5-dimethylpyridine (Ahrens, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 2062), 2:6-dimethylpyridine (Heap Jones and Speakman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1936), quinoline (Runge, *Pogg. Ann.*, **31**, 68), isoquinoline (Hoogewerff and van Drorp, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1885, **4**, 125; 1886, **5**, 305), quinaldine (Jacobsen and Reimer, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 1082), lepidine (Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1863, **16**, 431), acridine (Grabe and Caro, *Annalen*, 1871, **158**, 265) and hydroacridine (Decker and Dunant, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 1178) have been isolated.

Considering the manifold importance of pyridine and quinoline derivatives such as their application as starting materials for the synthesis of alkaloids and their derivatives, use of quinoline derivatives like thaline (6-methoxytetrahydroquinoline), kairoline (*N*-ethyl-tetrahydroquinoline), kairidine (1-oxy-*N*-methyltetrahydroquinoline), plasmoguin, analgen (*N*-acetyl-3-methoxyquinoline) in chemotherapy, their use as intermediates in the photosensitising dyes of cyanine class and so on, and also considering the possibility of yet undiscovered bases occurring in anthracene oil exhaustive investigation of the bases from anthracene oil was taken in hand.

The bases from anthracene oil (b.p. 270—350°) were extracted with moderately dilute hydrochloric acid, the acid extract freed from admixed neutral substances by steam distillation and finally the bases liberated with sodium hydroxide. The bases consist of a mixture of extraordinary complexity, the separation of the individuals by fractional distillation under atmospheric pressure was not possible as they show signs of decomposition. Their isolation by fractional distillation under highly reduced pressure was not success-

ful, as is indicated by the fact that fractions collected even within one degree's range did not yield crystalline salts with acids or double salts with ZnCl_2 , HgCl_2 , etc.

The above methods having failed, the possibility of conversion of these bases by oxidising the alkyl groups into carboxyl groups and then to isolate the individual carboxylic acids by fractional crystallisation was considered. The fraction $180\text{--}200^\circ/30$ mm., on oxidation with chromic acid mixture according to the method of Weidel (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 1992) gave a water-soluble resinous mass from which no individual acid could be isolated. Phenyl phenacyl esters of these acids (*cf.* Drake and Bronitsky, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 3718) have, however, yielded three nitrogen containing compounds I, II, and III melting respectively at 208° , 201° and 101° .

The quantity of these esters was not sufficient to allow their conversion into the respective acids; their identification (*cf.* Drake and Bornitsky, *loc. cit.*) was not possible due to the non-existence of similar phenylphenacyl esters of pyridine, quinoline and isoquinoline carboxylic acids. From the analytical value (N, 2.16) compound I appears to be phenylphenacyl ester of quinoline dicarboxylic acid.

Subsequently the bases were distilled under highly reduced pressure with fractionating column (rod and disc type) and 21 different fractions, each coming within a range of 5° were separately collected. The low boiling bases consisting of quinoline and homologues of pyridine were fractionated between $75\text{--}100^\circ/5$ mm. and the higher fractions between $80\text{--}160^\circ/2$ mm. Detailed investigation of the bases distilling above $100^\circ/2$ mm. was taken up, their boiling point under ordinary pressure being higher (above 250°) than those of the pyridine and quinoline bases already isolated from this source. Isolation of the individuals (a) from sulphuric acid solution by fractional precipitation with ammonia, (b) as their double salts with ZnCl_2 , HgCl_2 , copper acetate, etc., and (c) as hydrochloride, sulphate, chromate, acetate, oxalate, tartrate, salicylate was not successful. Their isolation by fractional crystallisation of the amorphous salts formed with methylene disalicylic acid according to the method described in Indian Patent No. 14616 (July, 1928) for the separation of alkaloids, was tried with no better result.

The picrates of the bases contained in the fractions b.p.80·5—110°/2mm. separated as a yellow crystalline mass whereas those of the fractions 110—5—160°/2 mm. were tarry semi-solid products. Isolation of the individual picrates from fractions 100—05°/2mm. and 105—10°/2mm. was not possibly even after repeated fractional crystallisation. This difficulty was, however, overcome taking recourse to a process of regulated cooling within a range of 10° in a thermostat. Following this process of fractional crystallisation for more than 100 times, it has been possible to isolate three individual picrates (IV, V, VI) from the fraction 100—05°/2 mm. and four picrates (VII, VIII, IX, X) from the fraction 105—10°/2 mm. of which X is identical with VI.

Colour and crystalline nature.	M.p.	Composition of	
		Picrates.	Bases.
IV Greenish yellow shining rectangular plates	230°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N*
V Yellow microcrystalline plates	181°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₀ H ₉ N*
VI Dirty green needles	212°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N
VII Greenish yellow thick needles	201°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₀ H ₉ N
VIII Dull yellow needles	203°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N*
IX Yellow shining plates	198°	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₄	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N

The melting point of the picrates (IV) and (VII) suggested their identity with those of 4:6-dimethylquinoline (m.p. 230°) and 8-methylquinoline (m.p. 200°). But the depression in their mixed melting points with the picrates of the synthetic 4:6-dimethyl- and 8-methylquinolines indicated their difference. Picrate (IX) was, however, proved to be identical with that of synthetic 5:8-dimethylquinoline (m.p. 198°).

The free bases have been liberated from the individual picrates by the action of alkali, the yield in no case was sufficient for determination of their boiling points. The bases liberated only from three of these picrates (VI, VII, IX) could, however, be analysed but the bases from all of the picrates have been converted into crystalline platonic chloride double salts *via* hydrochlorides. The ease with

* These values are calculated from the nitrogen content of the picrates and platinum content of the platonic chloride double salts.

which these are formed and their sharp melting points only indicate the purity and individuality of the free bases.

Of the fourteen possible monomethylquinolines (7) and *isoquinolines* (7) only 5- and 7-methyl*isoquinolines* are not known. It appears likely that the two bases corresponding to (V) and (VII) represent the two missing monomethyl*isoquinolines*.

As out of the 42 possible dimethyl derivatives of quinoline (21) and *isoquinoline* (21) only about 13 are known, it is not easy to identify the three new dimethyl bases corresponding to the picrates (IV, VI, VIII).

As there is no alkyl quinoline or *isoquinoline* base known the melting point of whose picrate approaches near that of (IV), (VI), and (VIII) and as the composition of the bases agrees with those of monomethyl- or dimethylquinolines or *isoquinolines*, it is claimed that five new bases have been isolated from anthracene oil, the presence of 5:8-dimethylquinoline in anthracene oil is also established.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction of the bases.—Anthracene oil (20 gals.) was extracted by shaking each time 2 litres of the oil with hydrochloric acid (1 litre, 12%) in a shaking machine for 3 hours. The acid extracts were subjected to steam distillation to eliminate the neutral and phenolic bodies mechanically carried over during extractions. The bases were precipitated with caustic soda, washed with water and dried, yield 1734 g.

Oxidation of the bases to their carboxylic acids.—The bases (56 g.) boiling at 180—200°/30 mm. were dissolved in sulphuric acid (25%, 135 c.c.) to which an additional quantity of sulphuric acid (448 c.c.) diluted with water (840 c.c.) was added. Chromic acid (280 g.) dissolved in water (280 c.c.) was gradually added to the acid solution of the bases cooled in ice with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain the laboratory temperature during 12 hours, and then kept in a thermostat at 70° for 4 days, till the solution became green. Chromium was freed as hydroxide by ammonia, sulphuric acid in the filtrate was removed by baryta and then the excess of baryta by carbon dioxide. Dilute sulphuric acid was carefully added to the solution of the barium salts and the precipitated barium sulphate removed. The free carboxylic acids obtained from above on concentration were obtained only as

a resinous semi-solid mass. The yield of the mixed acids was 12.56 g.

p-Phenylphenacyl esters of the acids.—The mixed acids were dissolved in alcohol and the volume made up to 250 c.c. with water; 142 c.c. of this acid solution required for neutralisation 180 c.c. of sodium hydroxide solution (0.1658 N). *p*-Phenylphenacyl bromide (8.2 g.) dissolved in alcohol (50 c.c.) was added to a concentrated solution of the above sodium salt and the mixture heated under reflux for 2 hours. The contents of the flask were then cooled, filtered and the residue freed from sodium bromide. The white solid, so obtained, however, did not melt sharply and yielded on repeated fractional crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and alcohol, three distinct compounds melting respectively at 208°, 201° and 101°; the first contains N, 2.16, $C_{39}H_{27}O_6N$ requires N, 2.31 per cent.; the quantity of the second and the third were not sufficient for analysis.

Fractional distillation under reduced pressure.—The bases (1620 g.) were fractionated into two portions (A) up to 150°/10 mm. (764 g.) and (B) above 150°/10 mm. (850 g.). The fraction (A) was fractionally distilled at 10 mm and distillate collected separately within a range of 10°. Each of these fractions was refractionated at 5 mm. and the distillates coming within the range of 5° separately collected, the residue from preceding fractions being mixed with the fraction to be distilled next. (B) was similarly fractionated at 2 mm. and the distillate collected within a range of 10° first and then again within 5° as in the case of (A). In the following table are shown the different fractions collected from (A) as obtained in the second series of distillations at 5 mm. with their refractive indices, densities and yields.

TABLE I.

Fraction.	Temp.	n_D^{40}	D_{40}^{40}	Distillate.
		Bases boiling below 75°		6.15%.
1	75-80°	1.5720	1.0294	4.84
2	80-85	1.5948	1.0585	7.81
3	85-90	1.6019	1.0661	15.00
4	90-95	1.6061	1.0706	8.36
5	95-100	1.6039	1.0780	8.04

Table II indicates the different fractions obtained from residues of (A) and the high boiling bases of (B) collected at 2 mm pressure together with their refractive indices, densities and yields.

TABLE II.

Fraction.	Temp.	n_D^{40}	D_{40}^{40}	Distillate.
1	80-85°	1.6051	1.0753	2.23%
2	85-90	1.6076	1.0753	2.86
3	90-95	1.6058	1.0778	4.28
4	95-100	1.6055	1.0783	5.65
5	100-05	1.6072	1.0794	4.64
6	105-10	1.6071	1.0802	2.55
7	110-15	1.6019	1.0812	0.74
8	115-20	1.6051	1.0819	0.47
9	120-25	1.6105	1.0919	0.63
10	125-30	1.6289	1.1074	2.01
11	130-35	1.6448	1.1035	2.15
12	135-40	1.6445	1.1125	0.63
13	140-45	1.6448	1.1358	0.89
14	145-50	1.6588	1.1415	0.45
	150-55	1.6550	1.1424	0.80
16	155-60	1.6511	1.1450	0.28
	Residue			18.35

Separation of the bases as their picrates.—All the 21 fractions (Table I and II) gave picrates, those obtained from the fractions 1 to 5 (Table I) as also from 1 to 6 (Table II) were yellow crystalline solids and melt within a wide range of temperature. Picrates from fractions 7—16 (Table II) came as brownish-black tarry products. The individual picrates were isolated from fractions 100—105°/2 mm. and 105—110°/2 mm. by repeated fractional crystallisation from alcohol by regulated cooling within a range of 10° in a thermostat and the melting points of all the fractions carefully recorded, till the m.p. of any particular fraction was within a range of 1° and remained unaltered on further crystallisation.

Picrates from fraction b.p. 100-105°/ 2 mm. (5, Table II).—To the bases (40 g.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (350 c.c.) was added picric acid (50 g.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (350 c.c.). The mixture was warmed on a water-bath and then allowed to cool when the picrates separated as a yellow crystalline mass, m.p. 170—85°.

Explanation of the chart.—R indicates residue, S indicates solution; R₁ and S₁ mean respectively residue and solution from R on crystallisation. R₂ and SR₁ mean respectively residue and solution from R₁. Similarly RS₁ and SS₁ mean respectively residue and solution from S₁; R(RS₁) and S(RS₁) mean respectively the residue and solution from RS₁ crystallised and so on.

The *picrate* (IV) was isolated from the residue R_5 as greenish-yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 230° , yield 0.52 g. (Found: N, 14.52. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.76 per cent). The mixed melting point with the *picrate* (m.p. 230°) of 4:6-dimethylquinoline, prepared from *p*-toluidine and methylene acetone (*Annalen*, 1890, 245, 360), was below 200° . The platonic chloride double salt made from the hydrochloride of the free base (oil), obtained from the *picrate* by the action of potassium hydroxide and extraction with ether, crystallised from water as dull yellow needles, m.p. 220° . (Found: Pt, 26.95. $[C_{11}H_{11}N, HCl]_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 26.95 per cent).

The *picrate* (V) isolated from the residue indicated as $R(SR_2)$ and also from $R(RRRSR_1)$ separated as yellow microcrystalline plates, m.p. 181° , yield 1.56 g. (Found: N 15.31. $C_{16}H_{12}O_7N_4$ requires N, 15.05 per cent). The *free base*, liberated from the *picrate*, was a thick colourless oil and became coloured in contact with air. The *platonic chloride double salt*, obtained from the hydrochloride, crystallised from water as yellow microneedles, m. p. $202-3^\circ$. (Found: Pt, 28.35. $[C_{10}H_9N, HCl]_2 Pt Cl_4$ requires Pt, 28.02 per cent).

The *picrate* (VI) was isolated from $R(RRRRS_1)$ and $R(RSRRS_1)$ as dirty green needles, m.p. 212° , yield 2.35 g. (Found: N, 14.42. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.76 per cent). The *free base* contained N, 9.02. $C_{11}H_{11}N$ requires N, 8.91 per cent. The *platonic chloride double salt* crystallised from water in orange-yellow needles, m.p. $256-57^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 27.01. $[C_{11}H_{11}N, HCl]_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 26.95 per cent).

Isolation of the individual picrates from fraction b.p. $105-110^\circ/2$ mm. (6, Table II) was effected similarly as from fraction $100-5^\circ/2$ mm.

The *picrate* (VII) was isolated from the residue R_4 as greenish-yellow thick needles, m.p. 201° ; yield 2.54 g. (Found ; N, 14.82. $C_{16}H_{12}O_7N_4$ requires N, 15.05 per cent). The mixed melting point with the *picrate* (m.p. 200°) of 8-methylquinoline, prepared from *o*-toluidine (Skraup, *Monatsh*, 1881, 2, 153) was below 175° .

The *free base* separated as a thick colourless oil and emitted pungent smell at 100° . (Found: N, 10.10. $C_{10}H_9N$ requires N, 9.79 per cent). The *platonic chloride double salt* crystallised from water in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 207° . (Found: Pt, 27.98. $[C_{10}H_9N, HCl]_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 28.04 per cent).

The *picrate* (VIII) was obtained from $R(RSRSR_1)$ by one more crystallisation as needles, m.p. 203° ; yield, 0.53 g. (Found: N, 14.58.

$C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.76 per cent). The *platinic chloride double salt* crystallised from water as yellow needles, m.p. 218° (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 26.93. $[C_{11}H_{11}N, HCl]_2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 26.95 per cent).

The *picrate* (IX) was obtained from $R(RRSR_1)$ as yellow shining plates, m.p. 198° , yield 2.84 g. (Found: N, 14.59. $C_{17}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.76 per cent). The mixed melting point with the *picrate* (m.p. 198°) of 5:8-dimethylquinoline prepared from 1:4:2-xylylidine (Berend, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 3165) was undepressed proving their identity. The *free base* is a colourless oil. (Found: N, 8.68. $C_{11}H_{11}N$ requires N, 8.91 per cent). The *platinic chloride double salt* crystallised from water in yellow needles, m.p. 234° (decomp.). (Found: Pt, 26.81. $[C_{11}H_{11}N, HCl]_2PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 26.95 per cent). The *chromate* crystallised from water in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 149° . The mixed melting points of the *platinic chloride double salt* and the *chromate* with those of the synthetic base remained undepressed.

The *picrate* (VI) was also obtained from $R(RRRS_1)$ and was proved identical with the compound obtained from fraction b.p. ($105^\circ/2$ mm.).

SUMMARY.

1. The mixture of the sodium salts of the carboxylic acids obtained from the fraction b.p. $180-200^\circ/30$ mm. by oxidation, has yielded with phenylphenacyl bromide three distinct esters, m.p. 208° , 201° and 101° . The first one appears from its composition to be derived from quinoline or isoquinoline dicarboxylic acid.

2. The fractions b.p. $100-105^\circ/2$ mm. and $105-110^\circ/2$ mm. give a mixture of yellow crystalline picrates from which after repeated fractional crystallisations under regulated cooling within a range of 10° , it has been possible to isolate six distinct and individual picrates (IV—IX). All of these picrates have been converted into the *platinic chloride double salts* possessing sharp m.p. *via* the free base and the hydrochloride. From the analytical values of the free bases obtained from VI, VII and IX and the composition of the picrates and the *platinic chloride double salts* it is claimed that five new bases have been isolated from anthracene oil, the presence of 5:8-dimethylquinoline in it is also established.

3. Work on the synthesis of 5- and 7-methylisoquinolines as also on the isolation of the individual bases contained in the higher fractions is under progress.

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